

Syntheses of some Cinnamoylcoumaran-3-ones

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Five 4'-methoxyphenyl-2-cinnamoyloxyacetophenones have been obtained by reaction of the related hydroxyacetophenones with *p*-methoxycinnamic acid using pyridine as a solvent and POCl₃. Bromination with CuBr₂ yielded the ω -bromo-ester, which on Baker-Venkataraman rearrangement gave the title compounds, the structures of which were confirmed by analysis and spectral data.

VERY few cinnamoylcoumaran-3-ones have been reported so far although the derivatives of 2-acylcoumaran-3-ones have been found to possess a wide range of physiological activities¹. Auwers² prepared 5-methyl-2-cinnamoylcoumaran-3-ones, while Marathey and Wadodkar³ obtained similar compounds by a different procedure. Synthesis of a few cinnamoylcoumaran-3-ones was therefore undertaken.

In the present study, the 2-hydroxyacetophenones (1a-e) were first converted to the esters (2a-e) using a solution of acetophenone and *p*-methoxycinnamic acid in dry pyridine and adding POCl₃ with stirring. The esters thus obtained were brominated with CuBr₂ in dioxane to obtain the ω -bromoacetophenones (3a-e). The cinnamoyl- ω -bromoacetophenones on gentle refluxing in dioxane in presence of powdered KOH (Baker-Venkataraman rearrangement), led to the cyclisation of the intermediates (4a-e)³. All the coumaran-3-ones produced deep colour with neutral ferric chloride and were soluble in alkali. Their elemental analysis and spectral data confirmed the structure. All the compounds showed ir bands at 1 610-1 590 (C=O) and ~990 cm⁻¹ (vinyl).

Experimental

All melting points were recorded in open capillaries and are uncorrected.

2-Cinnamoyloxyacetophenones (2a-e): A solution of hydroxyacetophenone (0.065 mol) in dry pyridine (5 ml) was mixed with *p*-methoxycinnamic acid (0.07 mol). To it phosphorus oxychloride (0.6 ml) was added and stirring continued for 1 h. The content was then poured into ice-HCl and the resulting solid was worked up and crystallised from methanol: 2a (85%), 109-10°; 2b (78%), 122-23°; 2c (80%), 114-15°; 2d (67%), 85-6°; 2e (78%), 99-100°.

***p*-Methoxy-2-cinnamoyloxy- ω -bromoacetophenones (3a-e):** Finely powdered copper(II) bromide (0.02

a; R₁ = R₂ = H, b; R₁ = H, R₂ = Cl, c; R₁ = H, R₂ = CH₃, d; R₁ = Br, R₂ = Cl, e; R₁ = Br, R₂ = CH₃

mol) was added to dry dioxane (40 ml) and the mixture was refluxed for 30 min. To it 2-cinnamoyloxyacetophenone (2; 0.01 mol) was added and refluxed for a further 2 h, when a grey-white precipitate of copper(I) bromide separated. The mixture was cooled and filtered. The filtrate was concentrated to remove dioxane as much as possible and diluted with water. The resulting solid was crystallised from ethyl acetate: 3a (65%), 89–91°; 3b (70%), 97–8°; 3c (60%), 108–0°; 3d (50%), low m.p.; 3e (55%), 110–11°.

p-Methoxy-2-cinnamoylcoumaran-3-ones (5a–e): A mixture of *p*-methoxy-2-cinnamoyloxy- ω -bromoacetophenone (3; 0.01 mol), anhydrous dioxane (20 ml) and powdered potassium hydroxide (0.03 mol) was refluxed for 0.5 h and then cooled and poured into ice-HCl. The resulting yellowish solid was washed, dried and crystallised from ethyl acetate: 5a (60%), m.p. 109–10° (Found: C, 72.8, H, 4.0. C₁₈H₁₄O₄ requires: C, 73.4, H, 4.7%); 5b (58%), m.p. 138–39° (Found: C, 66.0; H, 4.0. C₁₈H₁₄O₄Cl requires: C, 65.7, H, 3.2%); 5c (55%), 127–28° (Found: C, 74.8, H, 4.7. C₁₉H₁₆O₄ requires: C, 74.0, H, 5.1%); δ (CDCl₃) 2.40 (s, CH₃–3H), 3.81 (3H, s, OCH₃), a doublet centering at δ 6.90 accounts for olefinic proton (*J* 10 Hz) indicating it to be *trans*-aligned, the other

olefinic proton appearing as doublet centering at δ 7.70 (*J* 10 Hz), the remaining eight protons appear in the aromatic region at δ 7.2–7.9; 5d (62%), 200–01° (Found: C, 58.0; H, 2.9. C₁₈H₁₄O₄ClBr requires: C, 57.4, H, 3.1%); δ (CDCl₃) 3.85 (3H, s, OCH₃), 6.95 (1H, d, *J* 10 Hz), 7.20–8.10 (8H, m); *m/e* at 408 corresponds the molecular ion and important peaks at *m/e* 406, 366, 364, 174, 159 and 134; 5e (6.2%) 155–56° (Found: C, 56.2; H, 4.0. C₁₉H₁₆O₄Br requires: C, 56.3; H, 3.8%).

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References

1. H. ALKABIEBOLOG and P. APOTAKARE, *Chem. Abstr.*, 1965, 62, 6337.
2. K. AUWERS, *Chem. Ber.*, 1919, 43, 2196.
3. M. G. MARATHEY and K. N. WADOKAR, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1973, 11, 968.
4. K. D. BANERJI and D. PODDAR, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1976, 53, 1119.
5. K. D. BANERJI and D. PODDAR, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1979, 56, 905.